

NOVEL TRI-COORDINATED CHIRAL HONEYCOMBS

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SUMMARY

A combined experimental and modelling study has been carried out on the in-plane and out-of-plane mechanical properties of a family of tri-coordinated chiral honeycombs. Selection of honeycomb geometry enables both positive and negative in-plane Poisson's ratios, including one example of negative in-plane but positive out-of-plane bending response.

Keywords: negative Poisson's ratio, auxetic, honeycomb, elastic constants, mechanical properties

INTRODUCTION

In the drive to develop new and advanced materials for structural applications, factors to consider include how to achieve reduced weight and improved drapeability or conformability (doubly-curved surfaces). The ability to imbue the material, or the system within which the material is incorporated, with smart or intelligent functionality for adaptive control or structural health monitoring capabilities, for example, is also desirable. The lightweight requirement often points to the use of a honeycomb material incorporated within a composite sandwich panel construction. Double curvature, required in nose cones or other body parts for automotive and aerospace vehicles for example, can be achieved with minimum material wastage and damage during production by designing the honeycomb to possess auxetic (negative Poisson's ratio) response [1]. The classic example of how to achieve auxetic functionality is through modification of the geometry of a conventional (positive Poisson's ratio) honeycomb comprising regular hexagonal cells into one in which the hexagonal cells adopt a re-entrant hexagon shape (Figure 1). The re-entrant hexagonal honeycomb is auxetic when deformation is predominantly via flexing or hinging of the cell walls (ligaments) [2-4].

A novel chiral honeycomb comprising a regular array of cylinders interconnected by ligaments, with each cylinder having 6 tangentially-attached ligaments, was reported in the 1990s [5,6]. Figure 2 shows an example of such a honeycomb produced using rapid prototyping techniques [7]. This honeycomb displays isotropic in-plane auxetic response with Poisson's ratio $\nu = -1$. Further, the cylinders in the chiral honeycomb provide enhanced through-thickness compression response [8] whilst the ligaments provide improved through-thickness shear response [9]. Sensors can be embedded within the cylinders or attached to the ligaments for structural health monitoring capability.

Recently, an expanded range of honeycombs comprising cylinders interconnected by ligaments has been investigated [7,10,11]. This has included honeycombs having 3 and

4 ligaments attached to each node, and also attaching nodes not only to opposite sides of the connecting ligaments (creating the chiral configuration), but also on the same side of the connecting ligament to create a so-called antichiral honeycomb (i.e. one in which nearest-neighbour cylinders have opposite chirality). The interest in pursuing cylinder-ligament honeycombs with reduced number of connecting ligaments arises since they have lower weight than the equivalent 6-connected (hexachiral) system. We have also developed 3-connected cylinder-ligament hybrids based on the re-entrant hexagonal honeycomb geometry [11].

Figure 1 (a) Hexagonal and (b) Re-entrant Hexagonal honeycombs.

Figure 2 Hexachiral honeycomb [5,6] produced using rapid prototyping [7].

In this paper we report modelling and experimental studies into four cylinder-ligament honeycombs, all comprising of tri-coordinated cylinders (i.e. 3 ligaments per cylinder). Previously, the in-plane Young's moduli and Poisson's ratios were presented as a function of key geometrical parameters (ligament length, cylinder radius and cylinder/ligament thickness) [7,11]. In this paper, the in-plane elastic constants are presented as a function of honeycomb density. Out-of-plane bending simulations [11] are also included, demonstrating interesting consequences of the influence of the cylinders on the honeycomb mechanical response which are not present in the ligament-only systems (Figure 1).

HONEYCOMB GEOMETRIES

The cylinder-ligament systems considered in this paper are shown in Figure 3. All 4 systems are based on the same hexagonal symmetric cylinder pattern, with the different honeycomb geometries achieved by the ligament connectivity. The trichiral honeycomb (Fig. 3a) is derived from the original hexachiral honeycomb (Fig. 2) by removing the central cylinder (plus connecting ligaments) from the surrounding 6 nearest neighbour cylinders. Connected cylinders are located on opposite sides of the connecting ligament. Ligaments connecting cylinders having different x coordinates have length L_1 , and those connecting cylinders having the same x coordinate have length L_2 . For the hexagonal symmetric cylinder pattern, $L_1 = L_2$. Ligaments and cylinders have common thickness t , and cylinders have radius r . The re-entrant trichiral honeycomb (Fig. 3b) is derived from the trichiral honeycomb by moving the connecting L_2 ligaments along x by one half repeat unit. This requires $L_2 = 2L_1$ for the re-entrant trichiral honeycomb. The anti-trichiral (Fig. 3c) and re-entrant anti-trichiral (Fig. 3d) honeycombs are derived from their chiral equivalents (Figs. 3a and 3b, respectively) by locating connected cylinders on the same side of the connecting ligament.

Figure 3 Schematics of (a) Trichiral; (b) Re-entrant trichiral; (c) Anti-trichiral; (d) Re-entrant anti-trichiral honeycombs.

EXPERIMENTAL

Honeycomb fabrication

Rapid prototyping and laser crafting were used to demonstrate cylinder-ligament honeycombs can be fabricated easily and from a range of materials using established techniques. Details are described in [7] and [11]. Figure 4 shows examples of a rapid prototyped duraform anti-trichiral honeycomb (Fig. 4a), a laser crafted cardboard trichiral honeycomb (Fig. 4b) and a laser crafted acrylic re-entrant anti-trichiral honeycomb (Fig. 4c).

Figure 4 (a) Rapid prototyped duraform anti-trichiral honeycomb; (b) laser crafted cardboard trichiral honeycomb; and (c) laser crafted acrylic re-entrant anti-trichiral honeycomb.

Mechanical properties characterisation

Honeycombs were tested under compression loading up to $\sim 1\%$ compressive strain using combined universal testing and videoextensometry. This gave axial stress vs axial strain and transverse strain vs axial strain data for in-plane Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio measurements, respectively. Details are described in [7] and [11].

MODELS

Finite element models

Finite Element (FE) modelling was performed using the ANSYS FE package, version 10.0. Previously the in-plane elastic properties of the trichiral and anti-trichiral systems have been modelled using both a representative volume element (RVE) with periodic boundary conditions protocol [7] and an extended array protocol [11]. The re-entrant systems have also previously been modelled using the extended array protocol. In this paper, the in-plane linear elastic response of the re-entrant systems is reported for the first time using the RVE with periodic boundary conditions protocol. Details of the RVE protocol are provided in [7]. Simulations were performed for varying α ($= L_1/r$) and β ($= t/r$) in turn, with non-varying values of these parameters being $\alpha = 5$, $\beta = 0.05$. δ ($= L_2/L_1$) = 1 for the hexagonal, trichiral and anti-trichiral honeycombs, and $\delta = 2$ for the re-entrant equivalents. Out-of-plane bending response was modelled by applying an out-of-plane displacement applied to the central nodes at two opposing ends of extended arrays with constrained centre nodes. Details for out-of-plane bending are given in [11].

Analytical models for comparator ligament-only honeycombs

In order to compare the FE model predictions for the cylinder-ligament honeycombs with the properties of the ligament-only hexagonal and re-entrant hexagonal honeycombs (Figs. 1a and 1b), the analytical expressions for these honeycombs deforming by concurrent ligament flexure, hinging and stretching are adapted from [4]. For example, the in-plane Poisson's ratio for x direction loading of a hexagonal

honeycomb deforming by concurrent flexing, hinging and stretching of the ligaments is given by:

$$v_{xy} = \frac{\sin \theta \cos^2 \theta \left(\left(\frac{\alpha}{\beta} \right)^2 + \frac{3}{2} \right)}{(\delta + \sin \theta) \left[\sin^2 \theta \left(\left(\frac{\alpha}{\beta} \right)^2 + \frac{5}{2} \right) + \cos^2 \theta \right]} \quad (1)$$

where θ is the honeycomb angle defined in Figure 1 ($= \pm 30^\circ$ in this paper). Similarly, the expression for E_x is adapted from [4]:

$$E_x = \frac{\beta E_s \cos \theta}{\alpha (\delta + \sin \theta) \left[\sin^2 \theta \left(\left(\frac{\alpha}{\beta} \right)^2 + \frac{5}{2} \right) + \cos^2 \theta \right]} \quad (2)$$

where E_s is the Young's modulus of the ligament material.

Density

The honeycomb relative density (ρ/ρ_c) is the ratio of the area of solid material, A_s , within a representative unit cell to the area of the unit cell, A_{u-c} [10]. The derived honeycomb relative density expressions are presented in Table 1.

RESULTS

Comparison of experiment vs model in-plane mechanical properties

Table 2 shows the comparison between experiment and theory for a selection of honeycomb systems. Generally good agreement is achieved for the Poisson's ratios, and reasonable agreement is achieved for the Young's moduli.

Density dependency of the in-plane mechanical properties

Figure 5 contains plots of the Young's moduli in the x (left hand side) and y (right hand side) directions as a function of relative density due to changes in α and β for the hexagonal and re-entrant hexagonal (top), trichiral and re-entrant trichiral (middle), and anti-trichiral and re-entrant anti-trichiral (bottom) honeycombs. For the hexagonal and re-entrant hexagonal honeycombs, the curves due to varying α and β overlap and the hexagonal honeycomb displays higher Young's modulus for any given density than the

re-entrant equivalent (reflecting the fact that the latter honeycomb has longer vertical ribs (L_2), but equal diagonal rib length (L_1) and unit-cell area when compared with the hexagonal honeycomb). $E_x = E_y$ for the ligament-only systems.

Table 1 Honeycomb relative density (ρ/ρ_c) expressions. $\phi = \cos^{-1}(1 - \beta)$;

$$R_1 = 2\sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{\beta}{2}\right)^2 + \frac{\alpha^2}{4}}; R_2 = 2\sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{\beta}{2}\right)^2 + \frac{\delta^2\alpha^2}{4}}$$

Honeycomb	$\frac{\rho}{\rho_c}$	θ	δ
Hexagonal	$\frac{\beta\left(1 + \frac{\delta}{2}\right)}{\alpha \cos \theta (\delta + \sin \theta)}$	$+\frac{\pi}{6}$	1
Re-entrant hexagonal	$\frac{\beta\left(1 + \frac{\delta}{2}\right)}{\alpha \cos \theta (\delta + \sin \theta)}$	$-\frac{\pi}{6}$	2
Trichiral	$\frac{\beta[(2 + \delta)\alpha + 2\pi(2 - \beta)] - 3[\phi - (1 - \beta)\sin \phi]}{2R_1(R_2 + R_1 \sin \theta)\cos \theta}$	$+\frac{\pi}{6}$	1
Re-entrant trichiral	$\frac{\beta[(2 + \delta)\alpha + 2\pi(2 - \beta)] - 3[\phi - (1 - \beta)\sin \phi]}{2R_1(R_2 + R_1 \sin \theta)\cos \theta}$	$-\frac{\pi}{6}$	2
Anti-trichiral	$\frac{\beta[(2 + \delta)\alpha + 2\pi(2 - \beta)] - 3[\phi - (1 - \beta)\sin \phi]}{2\alpha^2(\delta + \sin \theta)\cos \theta}$	$+\frac{\pi}{6}$	1
Re-entrant anti-trichiral	$\frac{\beta[(2 + \delta)\alpha + 2\pi(2 - \beta)] - 3[\phi - (1 - \beta)\sin \phi]}{2\alpha^2(\delta + \sin \theta)\cos \theta}$	$-\frac{\pi}{6}$	2

The Young's moduli curves for the cylinder-ligament systems due to varying α and β do not overlap. Varying β has a more pronounced effect than varying α and is due to the Young's moduli being proportional to β^3/α in the cylinder-ligament systems [6,7]. The trichiral honeycomb possesses higher Young's moduli than the re-entrant trichiral honeycomb. The lower Young's modulus for the re-entrant system with respect to the non-re-entrant equivalent is also predicted for the antichiral honeycombs in the x direction. However, E_y is higher for the re-entrant anti-trichiral honeycomb than for the anti-trichiral system and this has been suggested to be due to a reduction in a lower energy half-wave flexure mode for the ligaments of the re-entrant anti-trichiral honeycomb when loaded along y [11]. $E_x = E_y$ holds for the trichiral and anti-trichiral

systems, but not for the re-entrant equivalents – possibly attributable to the complex multiple deformation modes acting in these systems alluded to in the preceding sentence.

Table 2 Experimental and FE model in-plane elastic constants

	Trichiral $\frac{\rho}{\rho_c} = 0.094$	Anti-trichiral $\frac{\rho}{\rho_c} = 0.105$	Anti-trichiral $\frac{\rho}{\rho_c} = 0.180$	Re-entrant anti-trichiral $\frac{\rho}{\rho_c} = 0.179$
<i>Experiment</i>				
E_x/E_s	0.00078	0.00036		0.00071
E_y/E_s	0.00058	0.00041		
ν_{xy}	+0.69	+0.08	-0.11	-0.77
ν_{yx}	+0.66	+0.08	-0.10	
<i>FE model</i>				
E_x (MPa)	0.00041	0.00024		0.00076
E_y (MPa)	0.00035	0.00022		
ν_{xy}	+0.64	+0.06	-0.06	-0.77
ν_{yx}	+0.55	+0.05		

Figure 6 contains plots of the Poisson's ratio in the x (left hand side) and y (right hand side) directions as a function of relative density due to changes in α and β for the hexagonal and re-entrant hexagonal (top), trichiral and re-entrant trichiral (middle), and anti-trichiral and re-entrant anti-trichiral (bottom) honeycombs. The Poisson's ratios of the hexagonal and re-entrant hexagonal honeycombs are insensitive to varying α and β , maintaining values $\sim +1$ and -1 , respectively. $\nu_{xy} = \nu_{yx}$ for the ligament-only systems.

The effect of introducing cylinders in the non re-entrant systems is to progressively decrease the Poisson's ratio in the following sequence: hexagonal \rightarrow trichiral \rightarrow anti-trichiral. The decrease in the Poisson's ratio for the anti-trichiral honeycomb is large enough to actually lead to auxetic response over a large range of density. The Poisson's ratios of the trichiral honeycomb are largely insensitive to density variations through changes in β , but show a decrease in magnitude as density increases due to varying α . The anti-trichiral honeycomb shows an increase with increasing density due to changes in β , and a decrease with increasing density due to changes in α . $\nu_{xy} = \nu_{yx}$ for the trichiral and anti-trichiral honeycombs.

For the re-entrant systems, the magnitude of the negative value of ν_{xy} progressively decreases in the following sequence: re-entrant hexagonal \rightarrow re-entrant trichiral \rightarrow re-entrant anti-trichiral. On the other hand, the magnitude of the negative value of ν_{yx} progressively increases according to the same sequence. The Poisson's ratios of all the re-entrant systems are largely insensitive to density variations through changes in β . $|\nu_{xy}|$ ($|\nu_{yx}|$) decreases (increases) as density increases due to varying α for the re-entrant trichiral and re-entrant anti-trichiral honeycombs. $\nu_{xy} \neq \nu_{yx}$ for the re-entrant trichiral and re-entrant anti-trichiral honeycombs.

Figure 5 E_x/E_s (left hand side) and E_y/E_s (right hand side) vs relative density due to changes in α and β for the hexagonal and re-entrant hexagonal (top), trichiral and re-entrant trichiral (middle), and anti-trichiral and re-entrant anti-trichiral (bottom) honeycombs.

Out-of-plane bending response

Anticlastic (saddle-shape) curvature was predicted from the FE model simulations for the hexagonal and trichiral honeycombs, consistent with the positive in-plane Poisson's ratios predicted for these systems. Synclastic (dome-shape) curvature was predicted for all 3 re-entrant honeycombs, consistent with the negative in-plane Poisson's ratios predicted for these systems. Figure 7a shows the synclastic curvature predicted for the re-entrant anti-trichiral honeycomb subject to out-of-plane bending by way of example. Interestingly, the anti-trichiral honeycomb displayed anticlastic curvature characteristic of a positive in-plane Poisson's ratio honeycomb (Figure 7b). In the model, the honeycomb parameters were $\alpha = 2.2$ (short ligament limit), $\beta = 0.25$ and $\delta = 1$. For this parameter set the honeycomb is predicted to have negative in-plane Poisson's ratios (~ -0.47) when subject to uniaxial on-axis in-plane loading. The predicted anticlastic

curvature implies the in-plane Poisson's ratio for the anti-trichiral honeycomb depends on the loading condition (i.e. auxetic for in-plane loading and non-auxetic for out-of-plane bending). It has been proposed this is due to the cancellation of cylinder rotation (which drives the auxetic response) from the deformation mechanism due to the top (tensile) and bottom (compressive) surfaces causing the cylinders to rotate in opposite directions when subject to out-of-plane bending [11].

Figure 6 ν_{xy} (left hand side) and ν_{yx} (right hand side) vs relative density due to changes in α and β for the hexagonal and re-entrant hexagonal (top), trichiral and re-entrant trichiral (middle), and anti-trichiral and re-entrant anti-trichiral (bottom) honeycombs.

CONCLUSIONS

The trichiral honeycomb displays positive Poisson's ratio behaviour. Interestingly, the anti-trichiral honeycomb can be tailored to have positive Poisson's ratio (long ligament limit) or negative Poisson's ratio (short ligament limit) response when subjected to in-plane uniaxial loading. The auxetic behaviour in the anti-trichiral honeycomb is driven

by cylinder rotation. Under out-of-plane bending the anti-trichiral honeycomb displays anticlastic curvature characteristic of positive in-plane Poisson's ratio response, even in the short ligament limit, and is due to a cancellation of the cylinder rotation mechanism in this loading scenario. Auxetic response in the re-entrant systems is due to a combination of cylinder rotation and direct flexing of the ligaments. Consequently, the re-entrant honeycombs display auxetic response for both in-plane uniaxial loading and out-of-plane bending.

Figure 7 Curvature upon out-of-plane bending of (a) Re-entrant anti-trichiral honeycomb (synclastic) and (b) Anti-trichiral honeycomb (short ligament limit - anticlastic).

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